

Exploring Salient Issues in School Effectiveness Studies: A Systematic Review

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Article Info	Abstract
<i>Article History</i>	<p><i>School effectiveness remained one of the most influential areas of research in education. Many studies had been conducted by various scholars across the globe and investigated different relevant issues in the field. However, there has been a literature gap of systematic reviews that compile the methodology, instrumentation and scope of previous studies of school effectiveness. Therefore, the main purpose of this review is to identify salient issues of school effectiveness in the school effectiveness studies. To effectively do the review, different data bases and search engines such as the Google scholar, Scopus, Web of Science, Elsevier, and Jstor were used to search for the literature on school effectiveness. 1098 articles were found out of which 206 study articles were systematically found more relevant and later duplicates were removed using a Mendeley reference software which reduced the documents to 148 articles. The inclusion criteria followed was that all the open-ended articles, empirical studies, written in English, full text articles, published between 2009-2019, in the subject areas of social sciences, arts and humanities, and psychology, published in referred journals, were included in the review and all others that have not satisfied these criteria were excluded. By applying these criteria, a total of thirty-three (33) studies were finally used for the review. Findings indicated that school effectiveness studies mostly used quantitative methods, used questionnaires or scales as instruments for data collection. Similarly, most of the school effectiveness studies reviewed covered the scopes of secondary schools. It is recommended among other things that researchers should also focus on primary schools which are the epicentre of elementary education. There is also a need for the school effectiveness researchers to employ triangulation method so as to be able to generate a more concrete, strong and reliable data that will aid concrete generalizations.</i></p>
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Introduction

It has been affirmed that studies of school effectiveness have gained ground since the late 60s and early 70s (A. Ghani et al., 2011; Scheerens, 2013) when the US researchers Coleman and Jack et al first collected and published an idea that schools make little to no difference to individual performances and achievements (Coleman, 2013; Scheerens, 2015). This perspective raised a greater concern among educational efficiency scholars and practitioners, which led to the development of a school-effectiveness movement that invested heavily in various studies to determine the reliability or otherwise of what the American scholars identified. Conversely, the SEM studies showed that schools do indeed make a difference and have significant effect on the academic success of students given their social, cultural, or racial backgrounds (Kamazraqandi, 2014).

The effectiveness of school as a multi-faceted and multidimensional framework deals with the actualization of the school target, which in the long run affects the progress of the students in school (Akay & Aypay, 2016). School effectiveness is the degree to which a school achieves its goals in the context of inputs and outputs (Boonla & Treputtharat, 2014). It is a term often used to describe the efforts that schools are making to bring about improvements that will help to increase the level of achievements of students (A. Ghani et al., 2011). Similarly, Boonla and Treputtharat (2014) had defined school efficiency as the rate at which a school achieves its objectives on the basis of its inputs and outputs. Wallin (2003) has already emphasized before these perspectives that successful schools are the schools whose students perform better than expected in their academic, personal and social aspects. Perhaps that's why Döş (2014) postulated that successful schools provide students with ideal learning environments for self-realization, simply referring to the fact that they instill the desire to behave as functional members of their communities in students. Therefore, good schools have effective structures and learning environments to enhance the development of the students in their cognitive, emotional, psychomotor, social and aesthetic aspects of life (Ajayi et al., 2017; Balci, 2007; Ekundayo, 2019).

The role of ensuring school productivity lies with stakeholders such as educational administrators, academics, policy makers, donor agencies and international organizations. In a given context, policy-makers (legislators or parliaments) make appropriate policies and laws that define or prescribe the standards under which educational institutions should be successful (Adedeji & Campbell, 2014; Malik et al., 2014). The educational administrators exhibit leadership and management strategies to enforce these policies by providing the requisite support, equipment, infrastructure, human resources, supervision and monitoring and assessment of the performance of the schools (Sammons et al., 2011). Similarly, researchers contribute to improving school efficiency by conducting a series of investigations and studies to evaluate school efficiency rates and offer suggestions on how to enhance the areas that require further improvement (Akay & Aypay, 2016; Magulod, 2017; Scheerens, 2015). Donor agencies and other international organizations such as the International Students Assessment, the United Nations Development Programme, the United Nations International Children Emergency Fund and the United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization Often help to increase school productivity by evaluating school performance and providing financial support to enhance the standard of the school (Chiaha & Nane-Ejeh, 2014; Hallinger & Heck, 2010; Ibrahim et al., 2017; Setwong & Prasertcharoensuk, 2013).

Different studies on school effectiveness had been carried out by many researchers e.g. (Abraham et al., 2012; Adewale, 2010; Adewale & Abiodun, 2009; Ajayi & Ekundayo, 2011; Akeke, 2019; Akinola, 2013; Akinola & Adebakin, 2016; Dahiru et al., 2017; Fasasi & Ojo, 2014; Obasanmi & Obasanmi, 2012; Odigwe, 2019; Ololube, 2005; Taiwo & James, 2015; Ghani, 2014; Ghani, Siraj, Radzi, & Elham, 2011; Iyer, 2008; Maroufkhani et al., 2015; Talebloo et al., 2017) etc and studied many issues such as school effectiveness and quality teaching, school effectiveness and mismanagement, support and school effectiveness, teacher variables and school performance, school effectiveness and teacher empowerment, job satisfaction and school effectiveness, leadership skills and school performance, quality control and school effectiveness, etc. However, it was observed that there is a literature gap of systematic reviews that compile the methodology, instrumentation and scope of previous studies of school effectiveness. Therefore, the main purpose of this review is to bridge this gap by identifying salient issues of school effectiveness in the previous school effectiveness studies to help guide the researchers in determining the right method, instrument and scope while attempting to do their research in the field of school effectiveness.

1.1. Research Objectives:

The objectives of this systematic literature review were to:

1. Find out methods that are mostly used in the school effectiveness studies.
2. Identify the most frequently used instrument in the school effectiveness studies.
3. Find out the scope that is mostly covered by the school effectiveness researches.

2. Materials and Methods

This study as earlier explained is a systematic literature review on the salient issues of school effectiveness. Systematic literature review is step by step process which commences by selecting, identifying, organizing and synthesizing previous studies on the variables that the review intends to cover (Moher et al., 2009). This systematic review was therefore done based on five strategies identified by Moher et al., (2009) as shown in figure 1 thus:

Figure 1: PRISMA (Moher et al., 2009)

Different data bases and search engines such as the Google scholar, Scopus, Web of Science, Elsevier, and Jstor were used to search for the literature using a specific keywords “School Effectiveness”. As a result of this search, 1098 articles were found. 206 study articles were selected and later duplicates were removed using a Mendeley reference software which reduced the documents to 148 articles. In addition, the inclusion criteria followed was that all the open-ended articles, empirical studies, written in English, full text articles, published between 2009-2019, in the subject areas of social sciences, arts and humanities, and psychology, published in referred journals, were included in the review and all others that have not satisfied these criteria were excluded. By applying these criteria, a total of thirty-three (33) studies were finally used for the review. The framework of the review was made on the basis of a table that contained certain elements such as the location, reference details, year of publication, title, aims, level, research design, sample, instrument, and study findings.

3. Results/Analysis

Based on the review, results were established based on the pre-stated research questions as will be presented as follows:

3.1. Research Question 1: What methods are most frequently used in the school effectiveness studies?

Based on the review, it was found that majority of school effectiveness studies employed quantitative method. In this case, they used survey or questionnaire as their tool for quantitative data collection. Figure 2 portrays the above fact:

Figure 2: method used in school effectiveness studies

Information in figure 2 indicated that out of 33 articles reviewed, twenty-two (22) school effectiveness studies are quantitative, seven (7) used mixed method, three (3) used qualitative and only 1 used Delphi method. Those that used quantitative method include (Ahmed et al., 2013; Akay & Aypay, 2016; Al Ahbabi, 2018; Ali, 2017; Boonla & Treputtharat, 2014; D'Sa & Sheela, 2015; Deeboonmee & Ariratana, 2014; Fasasi & Ojo, 2014; Prasertcharoensuk & Tang, 2017; Talebloo et al., 2017). Others include (A. Ghani et al., 2011; Abraham et al., 2012; Adewale, 2010; Adewale & Abiodun, 2009; Ajayi & Ekundayo, 2011; Akinola, 2013; Al-Harhi & Al-Mahdy, 2017; Dahiru et al., 2017; Maroufkhani et al., 2015; Obasanmi & Obasanmi, 2012; Odigwe, 2019; Taiwo & James, 2015). All these scholars opted for quantitative approach in their respective studies on school effectiveness at different places and times. Apart from these studies, seven researchers namely (Akeke, 2019; Akinola & Adebakin, 2016; Ali et al., 2016; Alm et al., 2019; Magulod, 2017; Ololube, 2005) employed mixed method which comprised of both quantitative and qualitative approaches. However, three scholars that employed qualitative method in their school effectiveness studies are (Agezo, 2010; Carruthers, 2012; Tichnor-Wagner et al., 2016). The only one who chose to use Delphi method was A. Ghani, (2014). Based on these, it was clearly manifested that quantitative approach was used most widely among the scholars of school effectiveness studies.

3.2. Research Question 2: What are the most frequently used instruments in the school effectiveness studies?

Figure 3 shows the different kinds of instruments that scholars of school effectiveness studies employed in their data collections:

Figure 3: Instrumentation in school effectiveness studies.

Figure 3 indicates that school effectiveness studies used different instruments for collecting data in their respective studies. From figure 3, it is seen that out of 33 articles reviewed, 6 studies (Agezo, 2010; Akinola & Adebakin, 2016; Magulod, 2017; Ololube, 2005; Tichnor-Wagner et al., 2016) used interview, 1 study (Tichnor-Wagner et al., 2016) used focused group discussion, 2 (Ali et al., 2016; Alm et al., 2019) used document analyses, 2 studies (Agezo, 2010; Carruthers, 2012) used observation, 1 study (Akeke, 2019) used checklist. However, 29 studies (A. Ghani, 2014; A. Ghani et al., 2011; Abraham et al., 2012; Adewale, 2010; Adewale & Abiodun, 2009; Ahmed et al., 2013; Ajayi & Ekundayo, 2011; Akay & Aypay, 2016; Akeke, 2019; Akinola, 2013; Akinola & Adebakin, 2016; D'Sa & Sheela, 2015; Dahiru et al., 2017; Fasasi & Ojo, 2014; Magulod, 2017; Maroufkhani et al., 2015; Obasanmi & Obasanmi, 2012; Odigwe, 2019; Prasertcharoensuk & Tang, 2017; Taiwo & James, 2015; Talebloo et al., 2017) used questionnaire. Others also include (Al-Harhi & Al-Mahdy, 2017; Al Ahababi, 2018; Ali, 2017; Ali et al., 2016; Alm et al., 2019; Boonla & Treputtharat, 2014; Deeboonmee & Ariratana, 2014; Ololube, 2005). Therefore, this implies that survey instrument has been the most widely accepted and used instrument for data collection in the school effectiveness studies.

3.3. Research Question 3: Which scope is mostly covered by the school effectiveness researches?

To answer this research question, the review investigated the scope covered by school effectiveness studies and therefore the information is displayed in figure 4 thus:

Figure 4: scope of school effectiveness studies

Figure 4 illustrates that schools that often fall in the scope of school effectiveness studies are primary and secondary levels at the expense of tertiary institutions. However, secondary schools are mostly the scope of school effectiveness studies followed by the primary schools. From figure 4, it is evident that 29 out of 33

studies of school effectiveness researches focused on secondary schools (A. Ghani, 2014; A. Ghani et al., 2011; Abraham et al., 2012; Adewale, 2010; Adewale & Abiodun, 2009; Agezo, 2010; Ahmed et al., 2013; Ajayi & Ekundayo, 2011; Akay & Aypay, 2016; Akeke, 2019; Akinola, 2013; Akinola & Adebakin, 2016; Al-Harthi & Al-Mahdy, 2017; Al Ahababi, 2018; Ali, 2017; Ali et al., 2016; Alm et al., 2019; Boonla & Treputtharat, 2014; Carruthers, 2012; D'Sa & Sheela, 2015; Dahiru et al., 2017; Deeboonmee & Ariratana, 2014; Fasasi & Ojo, 2014; Iyer, 2008; Maroufkhani et al., 2015; Obasanmi & Obasanmi, 2012; Odigwe, 2019; Ololube, 2005; Taiwo & James, 2015; Tichnor-Wagner et al., 2016) while only 4 studies had their scopes in primary schools (Magulod, 2017; Prasertcharoensuk & Tang, 2017; Talebloo et al., 2017). Therefore, secondary school is the level of educational institution that attracts more studies of school effectiveness perhaps due to its relevance in providing middle level of education that is after primary and before higher education.

4. Discussion/Conclusion

Based on the results or findings of this review, it is clear that school effectiveness remained as paramount area of investigation among the researchers and practitioners of education since the 60s to date (Scheerens, 2015; Tatlah & Iqbal, 2012). Upon this ground, various scholars and practitioners of education invested heavily in it in order to identify causative agents of effectiveness and ineffectiveness of schools in order to strategize ways of improving the effectiveness of the institutions for producing quality output (skilled manpower) that will work in different capacities of human endeavour for achieving the overall societal growth and development (Oduma, 2018; Otonko, 2012). This review therefore studied previous studies of school effectiveness with the sole aim of identifying the methods, instruments and scopes to which the researchers gave much attention in the course of their studies. This was to bridge the existing literature gap which has not been filled by the write-ups. Based on the review of 33 articles selected from different data bases, it was found that majority of the school effectiveness researchers opted for quantitative method which compelled them to also use survey as their tool for collecting quantitative data from their respondents. Nonetheless, the review discovered that most of the studies cantered on secondary educational institutions while paying little attention to primary schools not to talk of higher educational institutions. It is thus paramount to suggest that researchers need to also focus on primary schools which serve as the epicentre of primary education upon which all other levels of education are built. There is also a need for the school effectiveness researchers to imbibe the habit of mixed and triangulation methods so as to be able to generate a more concrete, strong and reliable data because a data that is triangulated is much more reliable than the one-sided one (Creswell & Creswell, 2018)

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